

Detection-Based Localization of Passive Radar Receivers

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Abstract—Passive coherent radar (PCR) is a growing threat to air power. PCRs use ambient signals (e.g., television, FM radio, other radars, etc.) to allow covert operation and thereby make receiver sites virtually undetectable, which complicates the use of conventional countermeasures. We seek to infer information about the receiver location based on the system’s behavior, in particular hypothesized knowledge of detection performance as a function of specific aircraft trajectories. Given this detection-only record, the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) of the receiver position and the Cramér-Rao bound (CRB) on this estimate are derived. A Monte-Carlo simulation is performed for different detection records validating the MLE and CRB derivations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Passive coherent radars operate multistatically by exploiting ambient signals transmitted by illuminators of opportunity (e.g., television, radio, other radars, etc.). This allows receiver sites to remain passive and thus difficult to localize for purposes of electronic counter measures. Additionally, ambient signals often occupy frequencies not typically open for radar use (e.g. VHF and UHF). Vehicles that are designed to have low radar cross section at high frequency may have higher cross section at low frequency [1].

PCR research has significant scope from imaging to tracking targets. Research specifically on the topic of PCR receiver location is primarily focused on optimum receiver placement for a desired coverage area. In [2], the authors explore possible receiver locations based on specific terrain. In [3], the authors formulate a PCR system that illuminates a specific target path by optimizing a network of transmitters. Based on the target path, two transmitters are chosen and then an optimum receiver location is determined. In [4], optimum receiver placement for a space-surface bistatic synthetic aperture radar (SS-BSAR) is studied using the relationship between the information matrix and the geometric configuration. In [5], an optimal layout is discussed for a Doppler bistatic network to detect weather echoes. All of these studies focus on selecting a receiver position to optimize a particular coverage area.

Conversely, the goal of this paper is to model a bistatic PCR scenario where the PCR receiver location is unknown and must be estimated. Specifically, we propose a detection-based localization scheme. We assume that the bistatic PCR is part of a larger multistatic network. It is then reasonable to assume that the bistatic PCR would communicate to other

sensors in the network when it detects a target. The bistatic PCR receiver might report several things including range or angle of arrivals. However, to be conservative, we assume that we do not have access to the internals of the communication message due to the likelihood of encryption; hence, we only know when the receiver transmits (target detected) and when it does not (no target detected). The receiver transmission is modeled as a binary detection record. The detection record of the aircraft flight path is defined as binary detection results as a function of aircraft position. For this study, the detection record (r) of a probing aircraft flight path and bistatic radar constant (K) is hypothesized to be known in the estimation of the PCR receiver location. In future research, the efficacy of these and other assumptions will need to be investigated as research progresses. The authors of [6] use a similar approach in submarine localization by a sensor network.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. First, Section II illustrates and defines the bistatic PCR geometry and nomenclature, including the transmitter, receiver, and aircraft flight path. Using the bistatic PCR model, we describe the process to generate a detection record for the defined aircraft flight path. Section III develops the maximum likelihood estimator used to optimize the PCR receiver location. A short description on how to initialize the optimization is provided. Section IV derives the Cramér-Rao bound for the detection-based PCR receiver localization model. Section V describes the bistatic PCR simulation to verify the model, MLE, and CRB. Last, Section VI summarizes our results and conclusions.

II. MODEL

Bistatic PCR involves a specialized geometry defined by the bistatic triangle shown in Figure 1. The bistatic triangle includes the transmitter (T), receiver (R), and target aircraft at each of its vertices. The transmitter located at (x_T, y_T, z_T) and receiver located at (x_R, y_R, z_R) are both stationary, ground sensors.

The aircraft flight path is represented by N aircraft locations (x_n, y_n, z_n) where $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The range from the transmitter to the aircraft location ($D_{T,n}$) and aircraft to the receiver location ($D_{R,n}$) are respectively defined by

$$D_{T,n} = \sqrt{(x_T - x_n)^2 + (y_T - y_n)^2 + (z_T - z_n)^2} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Passive radar system model: transmitter (T), receiver (R), aircraft (A), transmitter-to-aircraft distance ($D_{T,n}$), receiver-to-aircraft distance ($D_{R,n}$)

$$D_{R,n} = \sqrt{(x_R - x_n)^2 + (y_R - y_n)^2 + (z_R - z_n)^2}. \quad (2)$$

In this PCR scenario, the PCR system records a binary detection decision (r_n) for each aircraft location (x_n, y_n, z_n) . The PCR binary detection result is defined as

$$r_n = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if detected at } (x_n, y_n, z_n) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The PCR binary detections are collected in a vector defined as the detection record:

$$\underline{r} = [r_1, r_2, \dots, r_N]^T. \quad (4)$$

In order to test and simulate the PCR receiver location scenario, a PCR detection record for a particular flight trajectory must be generated.

A. Detection record generation

To generate a detection record, the aircraft flight path is simulated. For each discretized aircraft location, a probability of detection is calculated based on the bistatic radar range equation and compared to a uniformly distributed random variable. If the probability of detection exceeds the random variable generated at the n th location, the bistatic PCR records a detection by setting $r_n = 1$. Otherwise, the bistatic PCR records a missed detection by setting $r_n = 0$. The probability of detection (P_n) is a function of the signal-to-noise ratio (S_n) and probability of false alarm (P_{FA}), computed as

$$P_n = Q \left[a_n = \sqrt{2S_n}, b = \sqrt{2 \ln(P_{FA}^{-1})} \right] \quad (5)$$

where Q is the Marcum Q-function defined by

$$Q[a_n, b] = \int_b^\infty \alpha \exp \left[\frac{-(\alpha^2 + a_n^2)}{2} \right] I_0[a_n \alpha] d\alpha \quad (6)$$

where α is a dummy variable and $I_0[\cdot]$ is a zero-order Bessel function [7]. The signal-to-noise ratio for each probing aircraft location is calculated as

$$S_n = \frac{K}{D_{T,n}^2 D_{R,n}^2} \quad (7)$$

where $D_{T,n}$ and $D_{R,n}$ are computed by (1) and (2), respectively, and the bistatic radar constant, formulated in [8], is defined to be

$$K = \frac{P_T G_T G_R \lambda_f^2 \sigma_B F_T^2 F_R^2}{(4\pi)^3 k T_s B L_T L_R}. \quad (8)$$

The bistatic radar constant consists of the transmitter power (P_T), transmitter and receiver gains (G_T and G_R), bistatic radar cross section (σ_B), signal propagation factors (F_T and F_R), Boltzmann's constant (k), system noise temperature (T_s), noise bandwidth (B), system losses (L_T and L_R), and wavelength (λ_f) calculated as $\lambda_f = c/f$, where c is the speed of light and f is the frequency of the transmitted signal.

The detection decision is a binary random variable with a probability mass function simulated as

$$p(r_n) = \begin{cases} P_n, & r_n = 1 \\ 1 - P_n, & r_n = 0 \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

To estimate the PCR receiver location, we for now hypothesize knowledge of the bistatic radar constant, with plans to address joint optimization of these unknowns in future work.

III. MLE

In order to estimate the receiver location, the following information is assumed to be known: transmitter location (x_T, y_T, z_T) , bistatic radar constant (K), probability of false alarm (P_{FA}), aircraft flight path locations $\{(x_n, y_n, z_n) | n = 1 \dots N\}$, and detection record (\underline{r}). The unknown parameters are the receiver coordinates represented by the vector:

$$\underline{\theta} = [x_R, y_R, z_R]. \quad (10)$$

The objective is to estimate the PCR receiver location based on the detection record defined in (4). Here, we employ a maximum likelihood estimator defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\underline{\theta}}_{\text{MLE}} &= \arg \max_{\underline{\theta}} \prod_{n=1}^N p(r_n | \underline{\theta}) \\ &= \arg \max_{\underline{\theta}} \sum_{n=1}^N \log p(r_n | \underline{\theta}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where the likelihood function $p(r_n | \underline{\theta})$ is computed as

$$p(r_n | \underline{\theta}) = P_n \delta(r_n - 1) + (1 - P_n) \delta(r_n) \quad (12)$$

with $\delta(\cdot)$ representing the Kronecker delta function. Optimizing the logarithm of the likelihood function mitigates scaling issues with long detection records.

An initial guess of the PCR receiver location must be chosen to begin the optimization. In this case, the optimization starting location for the PCR receiver was initialized to the PCR transmitter location. Within (12), recall that the probability of detection is a function of the expected signal-to-noise ratio (7), which in turn is determined by the ranges to the bistatic nodes. The transmitter range is given by known information, while the receiver range varies with the unknown coordinates (x_R, y_R, z_R) to be estimated.

IV. CRB ANALYSIS

The Cramér-Rao bound characterizes the minimum variance for any unbiased estimator and is frequently used as a benchmark for performance [9]. The CRB is derived as a comparison to the MLE. The MLE asymptotically achieves the CRB as the number of measurements goes to infinity.

The CRB is calculated for the unknown parameters $\underline{\theta}$ given in (10). The CRB is computed as

$$\text{cov}(\hat{\underline{\theta}}) \geq F^{-1} \quad (13)$$

where $\hat{\underline{\theta}}$ is the estimated parameter values, and F is the Fisher's information matrix. Its elements are defined as

$$F_{ij} = E \left\{ \frac{\partial \log p(\underline{r}|\underline{\theta})}{\partial \theta_i} \frac{\partial \log p(\underline{r}|\underline{\theta})}{\partial \theta_j} \right\} \quad (14)$$

where $p(\underline{r}|\underline{\theta})$ is the joint likelihood function. The ensemble of detection decisions has a joint probability mass function

$$p(\underline{r}|\underline{\theta}) = \prod_{n=1}^N p(r_n|\underline{\theta}) \quad (15)$$

where $p(r_n|\underline{\theta})$ is defined in (12). From (15), we can compute (14) as

$$F_{ij} = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N E \{ \beta(r_n, r_m) \} \frac{\partial P_n}{\partial \theta_i} \frac{\partial P_m}{\partial \theta_j} \quad (16)$$

where

$$\beta(r_n, r_m) = \frac{[\delta(r_n - 1) - \delta(r_n)] [\delta(r_m - 1) - \delta(r_m)]}{p(r_n) p(r_m)} \quad (17)$$

The expectation must be considered separately for independent and coincident instances of r_n and r_m . When $m \neq n$, the expectation results in

$$\begin{aligned} E \{ \beta(r_n, r_m) \} &= \sum_{r_n=[1,0]} \beta(r_n, r_m) p(r_n) \\ &\times \sum_{r_m=[1,0]} \beta(r_n, r_m) p(r_m) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

When $m = n$, the expectation results in

$$\begin{aligned} E \{ \beta(r_n, r_n) \} &= \sum_{r_n=[1,0]} \beta(r_n, r_n) p(r_n) \\ &= \frac{1}{P_n} + \frac{1}{1 - P_n}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Inserting (18) and (19) into (16) yields

$$F_{ij} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{1}{P_n} + \frac{1}{1 - P_n} \right) \frac{\partial P_n}{\partial \theta_i} \frac{\partial P_n}{\partial \theta_j} \quad (20)$$

where P_n is the probability of detection defined in (5). The same expression for the Fisher's information matrix appears in [6].

Using (6), the partial derivative of P_n with respect to a receiver coordinate is

$$\frac{\partial P_n}{\partial \theta_i} = bI_1(a_n b) \exp \left[\frac{-(a_n^2 + b^2)}{2} \right] \frac{\partial a_n}{\partial \theta_i}. \quad (21)$$

Using (2) and (7) along with the equation for a_n in (5), the derivation is concluded by defining

$$\frac{\partial a_n}{\partial x_R} = \frac{\sqrt{2K}(x_n - x_R)}{D_{T,n} D_{R,n}^3}, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial a_n}{\partial y_R} = \frac{\sqrt{2K}(y_n - y_R)}{D_{T,n} D_{R,n}^3}, \quad (23)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial a_n}{\partial z_R} = \frac{\sqrt{2K}(z_n - z_R)}{D_{T,n} D_{R,n}^3} \quad (24)$$

and plugging (21)-(24) into (20).

V. SIMULATION

To validate the MLE and CRB, a PCR is simulated following the model outlined in Section II. The transmitter and receiver are ground based sensors separated by 5 km and are pictured in Figure 2 represented by a 'o' and 'x', respectively. All locations and measurements are relative to the origin (0, 0, 0) km in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Simulation set-up: transmitter ('o'), receiver ('x'), aircraft flight path (box with dotted line), area of interest (box with solid line in ground plane). Specific sides of the box aircraft flight path are numbered 1 to 4.

The transmitter or illuminator of opportunity is a radio station with transmitting frequency of 88.5 MHz. The transmitter location and characteristics used in the simulation are defined in Table I.

The receiver location and characteristics are defined in Table II. The aircraft flight path is a simple box (100 × 100 km) pattern depicted by a dotted line in Figure 2 and at a set altitude of 10 km. Specific sides of the box flight path are numbered 1 to 4. Using the values in Table I and II and the defined aircraft flight path, the detection record given in (4) is generated.

TABLE I
TRANSMITTER CHARACTERISTICS

Symbol	Description	Value
(x_T, y_T)	transmitter location	$(-2.5, 0)$ km
P_T	transmitter power	50 dBW
G_T	antenna gain	30 dB
λ_f	wavelength ($f = 88.5$ MHz)	3.9 m
F_T	signal propagation factor	-3.5 dB
L_T	system loss	1 dB

TABLE II
RECEIVER CHARACTERISTICS

Symbol	Description	Value
(x_R, y_R)	receiver location	$(2.5, 0)$ km
G_R	antenna gain	30 dB
σ_B	bistatic radar target cross section	10 dBsm
F_R	signal propagation factor	-3.5 dB
T_s	system noise temperature	300 K
B	noise bandwidth	60 MHz
L_R	system loss	1 dB
P_{FA}	probability of false alarm	10^{-10}

In the simulation, the PCR receiver location is unknown. The PCR receiver location is assumed to be in a 20×20 km area of interest pictured by a solid black box in the ground plane in Figure 2. To estimate the location of the PCR receiver, the MLE optimization model described in Section III is used. To begin, the initial PCR receiver location is set to the PCR transmitter position. The optimization is performed using MATLAB's *fminunc* function with the MLE equation in (11) as the objective function. The optimization chose the PCR receiver location that maximized the probability of having observed the detection record.

In Figure 3, four one-sigma CRB error ellipses are shown. From the largest to the smallest, the CRB error ellipses were simulated using flight path 1, 1 and 2, 1 through 3, 1 through 4, respectively. This figure demonstrates how the CRB changes and the MLE is more accurate as the number of looks increase. Next, 100 Monte-Carlo trials of the MLE optimization model were executed with a detection record length of $N = 10^4$ using all flight paths. The 100 resulting estimates of the PCR receiver locations are also shown in Figure 3 and corresponds to the smallest one-sigma CRB error ellipse. In the second simulation, 100 MLE PCR receiver location estimates were generated for different detection record lengths. The variance of the estimates for each length was calculated to compare to the CRB. In Figure 4, the results from this test are shown. As the number of observations increases, the variance of the MLE and CRB lowers.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper simulated a bistatic PCR receiver location scenario based on a detection-only model. It was shown that an

Fig. 3. The largest to smallest one-sigma error ellipses use $N = 10^4$ data observations and correspond to flight paths in Figure 2, respectively: [1], [1 and 2], [1,2, and 3], [1,2,3, and 4]. The 100 MLE PCR receiver location estimates were generated using $N = 10^4$ data observations and all flight paths. The estimates correspond to the smallest ellipse.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the variance of the MLE PCR receiver location estimates and the CRB for each data record length for x_R and y_R using all flight paths.

MLE optimization was possible to estimate a PCR receiver location given the detection record of the penetrating aircraft flight path. The simulations verified the MLE and CRB derivations. This paper uses aforementioned assumptions: known detection record and bistatic radar constant. In future work, only the detection record will be used. Additional challenges include exploring PCR receiver location for multistatic scenarios.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Baker and H. Griffiths, "Bistatic and multistatic radar sensors for homeland security," *Advances in sensing with security applications*, pp. 1–22, 2006.
- [2] C. Hoyuela, J. Terzuoli, A.J., and R. Wasky, "Determining possible receiver locations for passive radar," *Radar, Sonar and Navigation, IEEE Proceedings* -, vol. 152, no. 3, pp. 206 – 214, 2005.

- [3] V. Anastasio, F. Colone, and P. Lombardo, "A procedure for effective receiver positioning in multistatic passive radar," in *Radar Conference, 2009. EuRAD 2009. European*, 2009, pp. 493–496.
- [4] C. Hu, T. Long, and T. Zeng, "The possibility of isolated target 3-d position estimation and optimal receiver position determination in ssbsar," *Science in China Series F: Information Sciences*, vol. 51, no. 9, pp. 1372–1383, 2008.
- [5] R. de Elía and I. Zawadzki, "Optimal layout of a bistatic radar network," *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 1184–1194, 2001.
- [6] S. Zhou and P. Willett, "Submarine location estimation via a network of detection-only sensors," *Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 3104–3115, 2007.
- [7] B. Mahafza, *Introduction to radar analysis*. CRC, 1998.
- [8] N. Willis, *Bistatic radar*. SciTech Publishing, 2005.
- [9] S. Kay, *Fundamentals of statistical signal processing: estimation theory*. Prentice-Hall, 1993.